

Reproduction: A Lightweight Method for Modeling Confidence in Recommendations with Learned Beta Distributions

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This paper documents our efforts to reproduce the experiment described in *A Lightweight Method for Modeling Confidence in Recommendations with Learned Beta Distributions* [Knyazev and Oosterhuis 2023] which aims to develop a lightweight recommender system with explicit confidence without sacrificing accuracy. Based as closely as possible off the original approach, we replicated this experiment. While the results obtained match the original results relatively well, the outcome of one research question differed from that of Knyazev and Oosterhuis.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**; *Learning to rank*; • **Computing methodologies** → **Uncertainty quantification**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproduction, Recommender Systems, Confidence, Uncertainty

Glossary

CMF Confidence-Aware Matrix Factorization.

LBD Learned Beta Distributions.

LBD-A LBD with adaptive binning.

LBD-S LBD with static binning.

MAE Mean Absolute Error.

MF Matrix Factorization.

NDCG Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain.

RMSE Root Mean Squared Error.

1 Introduction

This report presents our efforts to reproduce the experimental results of the paper *A Lightweight Method for Modeling Confidence in Recommendations with Learned Beta Distributions* [Knyazev and Oosterhuis 2023].

In this paper, the authors propose an approach to address the lack of confidence indication in recommender system decisions. In detail, there is no differentiation between highly likely and non-likely recommendations. The proposed solution is fairly simple. The authors aim to model user preferences as probability distributions that represent confidence by utilizing beta distributions.

*All authors contributed equally to this research.

Our reproduction effort includes the analysis of the experiment design and the reproduction of key experiments. We aim to confirm the findings or identify potential inconsistencies. Our analysis will provide details on the reproducibility of the experimental setup and the conclusions drawn in the referred paper. The structure of this report is as follows: First, the experimental setup from the original paper is described, followed by a section about our reproduction process. This is followed by a chapter discussing the results and conclusions. Our code/notebooks are published in our GitHub repository, it can be accessed following this link: <https://github.com/thuber19/ExDDS-2024-WS>

2 Experimental Setup

This section goes into detail about the setup of the original experiment. This setup was also used in our reproduction, since the code was easily available on GitHub and instructions for replicating the experiment were given. The experiment uses 10-fold cross-validation for model training, using 95% of the data for testing and 5% for validation. The cold-start problem was addressed by removing users or items that are not present in the training set from the evaluation set. In order to evaluate the models, different metrics are used for regression, classification and ranking. The metrics for regression are root mean squared error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE), whereas accuracy and average log-likelihood are used as classification metrics and two versions of the normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG@3 and NDCG@10) are used for ranking.

Random search was used for determining each model's hyperparameters. The models were trained using different embedding sizes and a range of learning rates. Furthermore, L_2 regularization was applied and the final parameters for each model were selected in accordance with the best RMSE on the validation set of the first data fold. Pearson's r and Kendall's τ , i.e. linear correlation and rank correlation respectively, were used for measuring the correlation between confidence and prediction error.

3 Reproduction Process

This section describes the steps taken in order to reproduce the original paper as closely to the original setup as possible.

3.1 Download Git

Since we already created a GitHub Repository upfront, we downloaded the GitHub-Repository mentioned in the original paper as a .zip file and extracted it in our own GitHub-Repository.

3.2 Install Dependencies

The Readme-File in the provided GitHub-Repository states a set of required dependencies to run the experiment setup.

The mentioned package *dotenv* is not available, since it is actually called *python-dotenv*.

Furthermore, the stated version 2.12.0 of tensorflow is not available anymore via *pip install* in commandline. For that reason, we ended up downloading it from <https://pypi.org/project/tensorflow/2.12.0/#files> and installing the wheel manually from the file. However, since there is no version for MacOS X with ARM processors available, we will continue with the oldest version available (2.13.0) via *pip install*. This also requires a version other than the newest one of tensorflow-probability (0.21.0).

Since this version of tensorflow has compatibility issues with numpy, numpy also needed a downgrade to 1.24.3, which led to a downgrade requirement for pandas to version 2.2.1.

The final commandline prompt for this step is:

```
pip install jupyter matplotlib numpy==1.24.3 scipy pandas==2.2.1
```

```
tqdm tensorflow==2.13.0 tensorflow-probability==0.21.0 python-dotenv
```

3.3 Setting the Project environment

Additionally mentioned in the Readme-file, the .env-file required the path of the experiment folder to be populated for the PROJECT_ROOT variable.

```
PROJECT_ROOT=/Users/tobiashuber/Documents/GitHub/ExDDS-2024-WS/
confidencerecsys2023-main
```

3.4 Run preprocess_data.ipynb

In the experiment setup provided by the authors, a pre-processing jupyter file (*preprocess_data.ipynb*) is included. According to the Readme-file, this needs to be executed first. The execution works flawlessly, given that the previously mentioned packages and versions are installed.

3.5 Run models

The authors foresee the training/running of the models as a next step. To do so, we execute the code chunks in the *run_models.ipynb* respectively.

3.6 Reconstruct Research Questions

After the model is trained respectively, we can continue with evaluating the given research questions. The authors provided jupyter notebooks for all four research questions (RQ1.ipynb, RQ2.ipynb, RQ3.ipynb, RQ4.ipynb). For that reason, the results to the research questions can be reconstructed quite straight forward.

4 Results and Discussion

The authors of the original paper name four research questions their work aims to address. Running the four notebooks corresponding with the research questions yields results that can easily be compared to the original results in tabular format (the grey columns represent our reproduced measures). In our efforts to reproduce the research conducted, the original outcomes and the outcomes achieved by us will be compared in this chapter.

4.1 Parameterization of the LBD model

RQ1 *What modeling of the parameters of LBD results in the highest predictive performance for rating prediction?*

The difference in results can be seen in Table 1, with yellow cells indicating the best performing setup. Overall, the values obtained in this reproduction effort are remarkably similar to those provided in the original paper. We only obtain a different value for the best performing setup in two instances, and in both cases the deviation between our best result and the original best performing setup are very small.

Regarding RQ1 the same conclusion is reached, that the highest overall performance is achieved by the confidence function v^{sum} with α and β bias terms.

4.2 Recommendation performance

RQ2 *Does our LBD approach provide rating prediction performance that is competitive with MF, CMF and OrdRec?*

Table 1. Performance for various LBD configurations.

Size	ν (·)	Bias	RMSE		MAE		Acc		Ave.Log-L.		NDCG@3		NDCG@10	
512	sum	-	0.7932	0.7931	0.6130	0.6130	0.3016	0.3016	-1.769	-1.769	0.9330	0.9330	0.9568	0.9568
512	sum	μ, ν	0.7864	0.7863	0.6058	0.6058	0.3092	0.3091	-1.760	-1.760	0.9339	0.9330	0.9568	0.9568
512	sum	α, β	0.7761	0.7831	0.5895	0.5959	0.3139	0.3090	-1.755	-1.757	0.9357	0.9337	0.9583	0.9571
512	norm	α, β	0.7852	0.8253	0.5942	0.6257	0.3140	0.2945	-1.818	-1.887	0.9336	0.9248	0.9572	0.9515
512	dot	α, β	0.8387	0.8649	0.6391	0.6648	0.2972	0.2767	-1.865	-1.857	0.9330	0.9069	0.9495	0.9406
256,256	sum	α, β	0.7850	0.8018	0.5964	0.6123	0.3133	0.2996	-1.774	-1.791	0.9331	0.9284	0.9570	0.9538
512+10	sum	α, β	0.7759	0.7843	0.5875	0.5961	0.4356	0.4254	-1.432	-1.450	0.9351	0.9329	0.9579	0.9565

The difference in results can be seen in Table 2, with bold text indicating the best performing setup. When it comes to the values obtained during this phase of the experiment, discrepancies in the values are quite small, apart from one region, which is highlighted in red. Significant differences in accuracy and average log likelihood occurred for both the MF (128) and MF (512) model. Since these models were also performing quite badly in the original setup, we conclude that these discrepancies will not influence this project any further.

Table 2. Average model performance from 10-fold cross-validation.

Model	RMSE		MAE		Acc		Ave.Log-L.		NDCG@3		NDCG@10	
MF (128)	0.7802	0.8082	0.5984	0.6197	0.2923	0.0739	-2.004	-5.717	0.9334	0.9273	0.9570	0.9533
MF (512)	0.7883	0.7883	0.6022	0.6018	0.2934	0.0758	-2.022	-5.743	0.9321	0.9321	0.9560	0.9560
CMF (128)	0.7760	0.7914	0.5936	0.6069	0.3226	0.3100	-1.777	-1.803	0.9338	0.9293	0.9573	0.9546
CMF (512)	0.7820	0.7796	0.5967	0.5965	0.2849	0.2907	-1.801	-1.804	0.9329	0.9338	0.9567	0.9572
OrdRec-U (512)	0.7821	0.7821	0.6043	0.6042	0.2322	0.2324	-1.881	-1.881	0.9343	0.9343	0.9575	0.9575
OrdRec-UI (512)	0.7765	0.7765	0.5896	0.5897	0.4187	0.4187	-1.569	-1.569	0.9349	0.9349	0.9578	0.9578
LBD-S (512)	0.7761	0.7831	0.5895	0.5959	0.3139	0.3090	-1.755	-1.757	0.9357	0.9337	0.9583	0.9571
LBD-A (512)	0.7759	0.7843	0.5875	0.5961	0.4356	0.4254	-1.432	-1.450	0.9351	0.9329	0.9579	0.9565

For RQ2, more discrepancies with regards to the best performing setup were found. However, since the question is not whether LBD outperforms the other models but only if it is competitive with models such as OrdRec [Koren and Sill 2011], MF [Koren et al. 2009] or CMF [Wang et al. 2018] we can also answer RQ2 in the affirmative and come to the same conclusion as the original experiment.

4.3 Evaluating prediction confidence

RQ3 Is there a stronger correlation between the confidence and accuracy of predictions by LBD than for CMF and OrdRec?

Both the outcome of the original paper as well as our own efforts clearly show that both LBD-S and LBD-A have significantly higher correlation between confidence and accuracy than the other models, with LBD-A having the highest linear and rank correlation in both the original setup as well as our reproduction. This can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Average correlations between the predicted variance and MAE of baselines and LBD from 10-fold cross-validation.

	CMF		OrdRec-U		OrdRec-UI		LBD-S		LBD-A	
Pearson's r (Linear Correlation)	0.079	0.0933	0.157	0.157	0.175	0.175	0.304	0.289	0.329	0.325
Kendall's τ (Rank Correlation)	0.043	0.052	0.094	0.094	0.112	0.112	0.194	0.181	0.216	0.210

Thus we answer RQ3 in the affirmative as well.

4.4 High-precision targeted recommendation

RQ4 Does the confidence modeling of LBD translate to higher performance compared to MF, CMF and OrdRec in a high-precision targeted recommendation task?

The results for this stage of the experiment are shown in Table 4 with values in bold indicating the best performing setup. The differences in the values are very small, except for MF, where the values show a considerable deviation. However this is unlikely to alter the outcome, since MF was not of much significance in the original experiment. In the original paper, the results clearly show a higher performance of the LBD model. In our reproduction, while the values are all quite close together, we only record a higher performance in three out of six cases, with the other half clearly showing the better performance of OrdRec-UI.

Given these results, we must answer RQ4 negatively. There is no higher performance of LBD when compared to OrdRec-UI and thus our outcome differs from the one obtained by Knyazev and Oosterhuis.

Table 4. Model performance on the high-precision targeted recommendation task for distinct numbers of targeted users.

	N = 100		N = 320		N = 1000		N = 3200		N = 10000		N = 32000	
MF	0.885	0.784	0.893	0.789	0.889	0.798	0.886	0.798	0.841	0.793	0.726	0.679
CMF	0.913	0.845	0.907	0.843	0.904	0.850	0.895	0.837	0.853	0.815	0.733	0.698
OrdRec-UI	0.962	0.957	0.949	0.948	0.932	0.931	0.910	0.909	0.863	0.861	0.747	0.745
LBD-S	0.947	0.915	0.944	0.932	0.932	0.925	0.908	0.899	0.861	0.844	0.747	0.731
LBD-A	0.971	0.980	0.962	0.963	0.949	0.939	0.925	0.887	0.877	0.848	0.751	0.732

4.5 Statistical Analysis

To conclude, we perform a statistical analysis between the values we obtained and the ones we were trying to replicate. In the case that our response to a research question is the same as the original paper’s response, observing no significant differences in the produced metrics would give us confidence in our answer. Alternatively, if our response differs, we would like to see a significant difference in the metrics. The way we carry out these tests is by focusing on a column-basis on the results above, then the difference between the original and replicated values is tested for normality with the Shapiro-Wilk test. If we reject the null hypothesis, i.e. that the difference is normally distributed, we perform a Wilcoxon signed-rank test, since this does not assume normality. Otherwise, we perform a paired t-test. The results can be observed in table 5, which includes the p-values obtained for each paired test. The highlighted cells represent the cases where the p-value is less than 0.05, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and to the conclusion that there is a significant difference.

For RQ1 we answered in the same way as the authors of the paper, but we obtain no significant difference only in the Average Log Likelihood and NDCG@10 metrics, which are half the metrics that preserve the best outcome. Nevertheless, we can still be confident in our answer because although the best performing model is different in some instances, both the original and our best scoring model have the same parameters, with size being the only difference.

For RQ2 our answer matches the original paper’s response, and similarly we find that all metrics have no statistically significant difference with the exception of the Average Log Likelihood.

We skip this procedure for RQ3 given the small sample of results available.

Lastly, from RQ4 we obtain that the only statistically significant differences found between our results and the original ones are for N = 10000 and N = 32000. Although this might seem to

contradict the fact that we answered differently from the paper, it is important to note that these two instances were the decisive factor in our answer. Therefore, the fact that these show significant differences increases our confidence in our response.

Table 5. P-scores for the paired tests

	RMSE	MAE	Acc	Ave.Log.-L.	NDCG@3	NDCG@10
RQ1	0.0460	0.0355	0.0226	0.1775	0.0360	0.0589
RQ2	0.0952	0.0665	0.1083	0.0360	0.0877	0.0840
	N = 100	N = 320	N = 1000	N = 3200	N = 10000	N = 32000
RQ3	0.1234	0.1572	0.1337	0.0721	0.0289	0.0383

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, our efforts to replicate [Knyazev and Oosterhuis 2023] showed that for the most part, the paper and accompanying project were well-documented enough to reproduce the experiments conducted with relative ease. Once the package issues were resolved, training the models and generating the results proved to be quite straightforward. The results yielded by this reproduction were very similar to those obtained in the original paper. A thorough analysis of these results concerning the four research questions posed by Knyazev and Oosterhuis allows us to draw the following conclusions: In terms of the best-performing setup, we get the same results as in the original paper. Furthermore, the rating prediction performance of learned beta distributions, the approach proposed in this experiment, is competitive with MF and CMF as well as OrdRec. We also find that the correlation between prediction accuracy and confidence of LBD is higher than that of CMF and OrdRec. Our findings differ in that the confidence modelling of LBD does not lead to higher performance than MF, CMF, and OrdRec. OrdRec and LBD both shared the highest performance in a high precision targeted recommendation task.

References

- Norman Knyazev and Harrie Oosterhuis. 2023. A Lightweight Method for Modeling Confidence in Recommendations with Learned Beta Distributions. In *Proceedings of the 17th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (Singapore, Singapore) (RecSys '23)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 306–317. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3604915.3608788>
- Yehuda Koren, Robert Bell, and Chris Volinsky. 2009. Matrix factorization techniques for recommender systems. *Computer* 42, 8 (2009), 30–37.
- Yehuda Koren and Joe Sill. 2011. Ordrec: an ordinal model for predicting personalized item rating distributions. In *Proceedings of the fifth ACM conference on Recommender systems*. 117–124.
- Chao Wang, Qi Liu, Runze Wu, Enhong Chen, Chuanren Liu, Xunpeng Huang, and Zhenya Huang. 2018. Confidence-aware matrix factorization for recommender systems. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on artificial intelligence*, Vol. 32.